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SPICY Deliverable D1.5

State of the art of Current Recycling processes and compatibility with the new lithium ion battery

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¹ Dissemination level: **PU** = Public, **PP** = Restricted to other programme participants (including the JU), **RE** = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the JU), **CO** = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the JU)

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Deliverable abstract

The deliverable sets state of art in terms of recycling process as well as relevant regulation for battery recycling and classification.

Deliverable Review

Reviewer #1: Willy PORCHER			Reviewer #2:		
Answer	Comments	Type*	Answer	Comments	Type*
1. Is the deliverable in accordance with					
(i) the Description of Work?	X Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a
(ii) the international State of the Art?	X Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a
2. Is the quality of the deliverable in a status					
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(ii) that needs improvement of the writing by the originator of the deliverable?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes X No	<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a
(iii) that needs further work by the Partners responsible for the deliverable?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes X No	<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a

* Type of comments: M = Major comment; m = minor comment; a = advice

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1. Introduction

Until now there are no facilities dedicated fully to recycling EV-HEV batteries. The EV-HEV has different chemistry in comparison to portable, tools and laptops batteries.

In addition, the high power of packs/modules and cells imposes a new way to manage the end of life.

The deliverable is targeting the review of the existing industrial processes for recycling lithium ion batteries.

2. State of the Art

The main solutions able to receive power battery mixed with household lithium ion batteries are based on thermal treatment burning all the organics and applying metallurgy approach targeting the extraction of Cobalt Oxide – this will not meet the 50% EU recycling rate requirement hence will not be a long term solution.

Globally, either classical or new battery technologies have an important CO₂ sources (up to 400 kg of CO₂ by tons of batteries). But we can note that actual solutions on household are based on thermal preliminary steps.

A comprehensive summary of published projects for HEV/EV car batteries are listed in the below table.

Country	Recycling-project	Organisation	Subsidies	Remarks
USA	Pilot plant in addition to existing recycling facilities for primary household battery.	Toxco Inc.	7,3 M €	n.a.
Japan	Installation of a pilot plant	JX Nippon Mining Nagoya University	11,3 M €	dedicated to Co and Mn Li-Ion batteries
EU Germany	Recycling of EV Lithium-Ion batteries ONLY R&D Project	Audi, Chemetall, Evonik Litarion GmbH, TU.	8,4 M €	LithoRec project www.lithorec.de , only R&D
China Jiangsu	Development of a pilot plant for 1000 t/a Li-ion batteries	Yancheng Ltd., Minister of Industry.	> 10 M€	Electromobility project. No further info's available

Table 1: List of recycling project dedicated to EV-HEV

There are no solutions on the market which apply hydrometallurgy to the recycling of lithium ion batteries (household of EV-HEV segments) despite number of R&D and pilot projects.

Current processes able to receive cells but not dedicated to EV-HEV are summarized in the next table.

Company	Country	Process
XSTRATA Corp.	Canada and Norway	Pyrometallurgy and then hydro
UMICORE S.A.	Belgium	Pyrolysis and then Hydrometallurgy with solvent extraction
MITSUBISHI	Japan	Metallurgy under nitrogen atmosphere and physical separation
TOXCO Inc.	Canada & USA	Cryogenic milling and hydrometallurgy more dedicated to cobalt
SUMITOMO	Japan	Metallurgy in rotating furnace with mix of other Ni-Co wastes

Table 2: Description of the processes at industrial level

UMICORE (Belgium): Umicore Battery Recycling H.Q. (III) is a subsidiary of Umicore S.A., a stock listed multinational material processing group. A battery recycling pilot plant has been tested in Hofers (SE) and is currently upscale and installed in Hoboken (BE). A capacity of 7,000 tons/a announced. The process is mainly a smelting, where Li-ion and NiMH batteries (and their production scrap) are feed without pretreatment. The smelter is able to recovered mixed metals as alloys containing Fe, Cu, Co, Ni.

Manganese, aluminum and lithium are trapped into the slag.

Solvents and other organic additive are converted into gases which are treated with efficient plasma torch process and good gas purification. Gas treatment is able to trap all fluorine products into solid fly ash send to landfill.

Figure 1 : UMICORE process for Lithium ion battery

Xstrata Nickel (Canada) has a smelting process of Ni-Co-concentrates from ore using electric furnace where waste batteries can be introduced. Xstrata collects batteries in Europe make thermal process of full batteries in Canada and then the cobalt fraction is sent to Norway for chemical treatment. As we can see with flow chart, Li-Ion batteries are heated/ treated in a furnace and hereafter integrated in the smelting process. Co, Cu and Ni, incorporated in the metal bearing matte are granulated and sent to hydrometallurgical processing plant in Norway.

Figure 2: XTRATA step 1 process: pyrometallurgy treatment

Figure 3: XTRATA step 2 process: hydrometallurgy treatment

SUMITOMO in Japan treats the lithium ion batteries in cobalt furnace working already with other metal scraps at 1600°C. The final fraction is an alloy sent to refinery. This operation is accompanied with dust /fly ash production as well as slag and sludge coming from cooling and water treatment.

Figure 4: Metallurgical process of Sumitomo (Japan)

Mistubishi Heavy industry (Japan) is a Japanese company specialized in heavy extractive metallurgy processes. This company has developed method of thermal treatment of nickel cobalt waste and has extended it to lithium ion batteries. It consists of thermal process under nitrogen atmosphere followed by physical separation of ferrous metal fraction, nonferrous and mineral (slag).

Figure 5: MITSUBSHI HEAVY INDUSTRY Process

TOXCO (USA) is an American company which originally dealt exclusively with primary lithium batteries from the army by a process of cryogenic grinding at -176°C . Recently the process was completed with wet step leading to lithium carbonate recovery. Subsequently society has developed a process dedicated lithium ion and is now addressing recycling of the batteries of vehicles in a program engaged by the U.S. Government to height of 9 M\$. Flow sheet of process is repeated below:

Figure 6: ToxCo process for recycling lithium based batteries

3. Compatibility with the chemistry of the SPICY project

At this stage the materials targeted in the SPICY project, as active materials or electrolyte, by the partners are summarized in the next table; this table was built from feedback of questionnaire proposed by Recupyl to each WP leader in order to fix the adopted materials.

Materials	Pyrometallurgy oxidative	Pyrometallurgy Reductive	Remark on thermal previous process	Impact and benefit of hydrometallurgy
Li_xMPO_4	No phase Change	Reduction more difficult due to phosphate slag	CO_2 impact	Selective separation
(x=Fe, Mn, Co, Ni)	No separation lost in slag	lost in slag	Fluorine emission Account in RE	Li recovered
Silicon	Totally lost in slag	High temp to reduce Si	Increase weight of slag Impact on Recycling Efficiency	Easily separated not soluble H^+ Silicate in OH
Coating C	Direct CO_2	Used as reducer	Impact on RE	separated
Coating $\text{AlO}_x, \text{SiO}_x$	Direct into slag	Formation of alloys	Impact on solid waste & on Recycling Efficiency	Selective separation
Lithium salts and electrolyte	Pyrometallurgy oxidative	Pyrometallurgy Reductive	Remark on thermal previous process	Impact and benefit of hydrometallurgy
Li Cyano Fluro Imidazol	$\text{Li}_2\text{O}, \text{CO}/ \text{CO}_2, \text{NO}_x, \text{HF},$	CN, LiF, CO	Recycling Efficiency, Gas effluents, Li lost	LiF, H_2CO_3 , HSCN, Imidazole
Lithium oxalate borate with or without F	$\langle \text{LiF}, \text{LiB}_4\text{O}_7 \rangle$ in slag, CO_2	$\langle \text{LiF}, \text{LiBO}_2 \rangle$ in slag, CO	Recycling Efficiency	$\text{Li}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4, \text{LiBO}_2, \text{LiF}$
Sulfolane	$\text{SO}_2/\text{SO}_3, \text{CO}_2$	S, $\text{H}_2\text{S}, \text{CO}$	Recycling Efficiency, Gas effluents,	redox and pH conditions to keep safe

We see that current pyrometallurgical processes cannot achieve a substantial recycling rate and development of dedicated process is mandatory.

In other hand we can see that the thermal processes are leading to:

- the destruction of all new and advanced lithium salts, generally having high added value
- the production of high level of gas emission ($\text{NO}_x, \text{SO}_2, \text{HF}, \text{F}_2$ and CO/CO_2)

In this case “cold” processes are mandatory.

This consideration is completed by the achievement of recycling rate (RE) imposed by the EU Directive EC-66-06. If we consider the chemistry LiFePO_4 versus graphite, we report here after mass balance is assumed according to distribution of cathode/electrolyte/anode in to market cell:

Recycling rate
Pyro process With slag and without carbon

Recycling rate
Hydro process

This chart is extracted from work provided by RECUPYL on market cells using LiFePO_4 cathode.

We can easily see that hydro processes applied to the chemistry of SPICY will allow achieving high recycling rate.

4. Conclusion

The existing processes are more dedicated to portable batteries and target mainly high value metals such as Cobalt and Nickel. Except US facility, no European facility is recovering the lithium fraction.

In another hand, facilities are not sized to recover iron phosphate based batteries as well as Si anode or LTO anodes.

Even in facilities operating the recycling portable/laptop batteries, no one is designed to recover the solvents, lithium salts and advanced anodes as well as the full carbon. In the meantime, EU Directive EC 66-06 imposes the electrolyte recovery as minimum of recycling steps.

5. Annex

5.1. ANNEX 1 : EU BATTERY DIRECTIVE

26.9.2006	EN	Official Journal of the European Union	L 266/1
I			
<i>(Acts whose publication is obligatory)</i>			
<p>DIRECTIVE 2006/66/EC OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 6 September 2006 on batteries and accumulators and waste batteries and accumulators and repealing Directive 91/157/EEC (Text with EEA relevance)</p>			
<p>THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND THE COUNCIL OF THE EUROPEAN UNION,</p>	<p>(2) The Commission Communication of 30 July 1996 on the Review of the Community Strategy for Waste Management established guidelines for future Community waste policy. That Communication stresses the need to reduce the quantities of hazardous substances in waste and points out the potential benefits of Community-wide rules limiting the presence of such substances in products and in production processes. It further states that, where the generation of waste cannot be avoided, that waste should be reused or recovered for its material or energy.</p>		
<p>Having regard to the Treaty establishing the European Community, and in particular Article 175(1) thereof and Article 95(1) thereof in relation to Articles 4, 6 and 21 of this Directive,</p>	<p>(3) The Council Resolution of 25 January 1988 on a Community action programme to combat environmental pollution by cadmium⁽¹⁾ stressed the limitation of the uses of cadmium to cases where suitable alternatives do not exist and the collection and recycling of batteries containing cadmium as major elements of the strategy for cadmium control in the interests of the protection of human health and the environment.</p>		
<p>Having regard to the proposal from the Commission⁽²⁾,</p>	<p>(4) Council Directive 91/157/EEC of 18 March 1991 on batteries and accumulators containing certain dangerous substances⁽³⁾ has brought about an approximation of Member States' laws in this field. However, the objectives of that Directive have not been fully attained, Decision No 1600/2002/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 July 2002 laying down the Sixth Community Environment Action Programme⁽⁴⁾ and Directive 2002/96/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 January 2003 on waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE)⁽⁵⁾ also underlined the need for Directive 91/157/EEC to be revised. Directive 91/157/EEC should therefore be revised and replaced in the interests of clarity.</p>		
<p>Having regard to the opinion of the European Economic and Social Committee⁽⁶⁾,</p>			
<p>Having regard to the opinion of the Committee of Regions⁽⁷⁾,</p>			
<p>Acting in accordance with the procedure laid down in Article 251 of the Treaty⁽⁸⁾, in the light of the joint text approved by the Conciliation Committee on 22 June 2006,</p>			
<p>Whereas:</p>			
<p>(1) It is desirable to harmonise national measures concerning batteries and accumulators and waste batteries and accumulators. The primary objective of this Directive is to minimise the negative impact of batteries and accumulators and waste batteries and accumulators on the environment, thus contributing to the protection, preservation and improvement of the quality of the environment. The legal base is therefore Article 175(1) of the Treaty. However, it is also appropriate to take measures at Community level on the basis of Article 95(1) of the Treaty to harmonise requirements concerning the heavy metal content and labelling of batteries and accumulators and so to ensure the smooth functioning of the internal market and avoid distortion of competition within the Community.</p>			
<p>⁽¹⁾ OJ C 96, 21.4.2004, p. 29.</p>	<p>⁽²⁾ OJ C 30, 4.2.1988, p. 1.</p>		
<p>⁽²⁾ OJ C 117, 30.4.2004, p. 5.</p>	<p>⁽³⁾ OJ L 78, 26.3.1991, p. 38. Directive as amended by Commission Directive 98/101/EC (OJ L 1, 5.1.1999, p. 1).</p>		
<p>⁽³⁾ OJ C 121, 30.4.2004, p. 35.</p>	<p>⁽⁴⁾ OJ L 242, 10.9.2002, p. 1.</p>		
<p>⁽⁴⁾ Opinion of the European Parliament of 20 April 2004 (OJ C 104 E, 30.4.2004, p. 354), Council Common Position of 18 July 2005 (OJ C 264 E, 25.10.2005, p. 1) and Position of the European Parliament of 13 December 2005 (not yet published in the Official Journal). European Parliament Legislative Resolution of 4 July 2006 (not yet published in the Official Journal) and Decision of the Council of 18 July 2006.</p>	<p>⁽⁵⁾ OJ L 37, 13.2.2003, p. 24. Directive as amended by Directive 2003/108/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council (OJ L 345, 31.12.2003, p. 106).</p>		

ANNEX III

DETAILED TREATMENT AND RECYCLING REQUIREMENTS

PART A: TREATMENT

1. Treatment shall, as a minimum, include removal of all fluids and acids.
2. Treatment and any storage, including temporary storage, at treatment facilities shall take place in sites with impermeable surfaces and suitable weatherproof covering or in suitable containers.

PART B: RECYCLING

3. Recycling processes shall achieve the following minimum recycling efficiencies:
 - (a) recycling of 65 % by average weight of lead-acid batteries and accumulators, including recycling of the lead content to the highest degree that is technically feasible while avoiding excessive costs;
 - (b) recycling of 75 % by average weight of nickel-cadmium batteries and accumulators, including recycling of the cadmium content to the highest degree that is technically feasible while avoiding excessive costs; and
 - (c) recycling of 50 % by average weight of other waste batteries and accumulators.

5.2. ANNEX 2 : SHIPMENT LARGE BATTERIES AND HAZARDOUS GOODS

Committee of Experts on the Transport of Dangerous Goods and on the Globally Harmonized System of Classification and Labelling of Chemicals

Sub-Committee of Experts on the Transport of Dangerous Goods

Fortieth session

Item 3(d) of the provisional agenda

Electric storage systems; large packaging for lithium batteries

Large Packaging for Lithium Batteries

Introduction

1. During discussions on lithium batteries at the thirty-ninth session of the UN Sub-Committee, it was noted that a Large Packing Instruction was needed for lithium ion and lithium metal batteries to accommodate batteries whose net mass exceeds 400 kg or for lithium battery packaging with a capacity exceeding 450 liters as stated in 6.1.1.1(c) and (d) of the Model Regulations.
2. Large format lithium ion batteries are becoming more common in the marketplace and the limitations placed on Packing Instruction 903 as stated in 6.1.1.1(c) and (d) of the Model Regulations do not provide for these larger lithium ion batteries. Therefore, PRBA and RECHARGE have proposed on the following page a Large Packing Instruction LP903 for Lithium batteries.
3. One point that requires clarification pertains to the existing provision in P903 for lithium batteries that exceed 12 kg and are manufactured with impact-resistant outer casings. These larger batteries are authorized in non-specification packaging. PRBA and RECHARGE believe it is not necessary to include the same provision in the proposed LP903 because the 400 kg / 450 liters limitations in 6.1.1.1(c) and (d) do not apply to the non-specification packaging used for these large lithium batteries over 12 kg. Therefore, the existing provision in P903 is adequate to address the packaging requirements for any lithium battery that exceeds 12 kg and is manufactured with an impact-resistant outer casing.

LP903	PACKING INSTRUCTION	LP903
This instruction applies to UN Nos. 3090, 3091, 3480 and 3481		
<p>The following large packagings are authorized provided that the general provisions of 4.1.1 and 4.1.3 are met:</p> <p>(1) For cells and batteries:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">steel (50A)aluminium (50B)metal other than steel or aluminium (50N)rigid plastics (50H)natural wood (50C)plywood (50D)reconstituted wood (50F)rigid fibreboard (50G) <p>Cells or batteries shall be packed in packagings so that the cells or batteries are protected against damage that may be caused by the movement or placement of the cells or batteries within the packaging.</p> <p>Packagings shall conform to the packing group II performance level</p> <p>(2) For cells or batteries packed with equipment:</p> <p>Packagings conforming to the requirements in paragraph (1) of this packing instruction, then placed with the equipment in an outer packaging; or</p> <p>Packagings that completely enclose the cells or batteries, then placed with equipment in a packaging conforming to the requirements in paragraph (1) of this packing instruction.</p> <p>The equipment shall be secured against movement within the outer packaging.</p> <p>For the purpose of this packing instruction, "equipment" means apparatus requiring the lithium metal or lithium ion cells or batteries with which it is packed for its operation.</p> <p>(3) For cells or batteries contained in equipment:</p> <p>Strong outer packagings constructed of suitable material of adequate strength and design, in relation to the packaging capacity and its intended use. They shall be constructed in such a manner as to prevent accidental operation during transport. Packagings do not need to meet the requirements of 4.1.1.3.</p> <p>Large equipment can be offered for transport unpackaged or on pallets when the cells or batteries are afforded equivalent protection by the equipment in which they are contained.</p>		
<p>Additional requirement:</p> <p>Cells or batteries shall be protected against short circuit.</p>		

5.3. ANNEX 3 : NEW CLASSIFICATION OF USED BATTERIES BY EC:

Until now the used batteries were classified into 4 classes according to the European Waste Catalog (EC regulation N° 1272/2008 of the European parliament and of the council) which is used for the classification of all non-hazardous wastes and hazardous wastes.

This classification in force from 2008 targets labeling and packaging of substances and mixtures, enables to have specific risks to materials and compounds on the basis of a comprehensive list of classified single substances in relation to their concentration in products.

These products are designed to form a global waste classification system across the EU. They form the basis for all national and international waste reporting obligations, such as those associated with waste permits, the National Waste Database and the transport of waste in national and trans-boundary transfer.

The classification was until now identified into only ONE category “**16 code**” with 4 sub-categories reported hereafter:

Actual Situation	
Waste Code	Current classification
16.06	Accumulators & Batteries
16.06.01*	Lead batteries
16.06.02*	Ni-Cd batteries
16.06.03*	Mercury-containing batteries
16.06.04	Alkaline batteries (except 16.06.03)
16.06.05	Other Batteries & accumulators
16.06.06*	Separately collected electrolyte from batteries and accumulators

This classification is related to batteries selected as specific stream.

Another classification under “**20 code**” targets the mixed stream and mainly coming from municipal waste.

20.01	Separately collected fractions from municipal wastes
20.01.33*	Batteries and accumulators included in 16.06.01, 16.06.02 or 16.06.03 and unsorted batteries and accumulators containing these batteries
20.01.34	Batteries and accumulators other than those mentioned in 20.01.33

However recently EC proposed a deep modification of this classification mainly by adding sub categories:

New proposal Added words in <u>Bold</u>	
Waste Code	New proposal
16.06	Batteries & Accumulators
16.06.01*	Lead batteries and battery scrap (e.g. plate waste)
16.06.02*	Ni-Cd batteries
16.06.03*	Mercury-containing batteries
16.06.04*	Alkaline batteries
16.06.05*	Other <u>hazardous</u> batteries & accumulators

New subcategories

16.06.07*	<u>Mixed batteries & accumulators</u>
16.06.05	<u>Ni-metal hydride and other nickel batteries except 16.06.02*</u>
16.06.05*	<u>Lithium batteries</u>
16.06.03	Other non-hazardous batteries and accumulators

This new classification, not yet fully approved, could deeply change the circulation of scrap batteries.

In the context of our project, EU member states categories Li-Ion batteries according CLP and Basel convention's 1090: non-hazardous waste as no LITHIUM METAL is found in lithium ion batteries (UN Class 9). However, Austria and Switzerland started to classify batteries in general as hazardous waste, arguing that all contain substances in a certain concentration, which would lead in human environment (e.g. nutrition's) to a threat of human health⁴.

⁴ This position does not take into account the encapsulation of active materials and then the lack of human exposure.

5.4. ANNEX 4: SOME REFERENCES OF THE LITERATURE

EC DIRECTIVE N°066/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council on battery management

EC DIRECTIVE N°053/2000 European Parliament and of the Council on the end-of-life vehicle.

EC DIRECTIVE No. 1907/2006 (Corrigendum 29th May 2007) and 2006/121/EC (Corrigendum 29th May 2007)

Guidelines for Life-cycle Assessment: Code of Practice', SETAC, Brussels, 1993;

Sustainability and the life cycle concept: international and interdisciplinary perspectives, Environ. Prog. 22 (4) (2004) D15;

Life-cycle approaches for assessing green chemistry technologies, Ind. Eng. Chem. Res. 41 (18) (2002) 4498–4502

ISO 14001, Environmental Management Systems ∅ Specification with Guidance for Use, HMSO, London, 1996.],

EU Eco-Management and Audit Schemes (EMAS) [Council Regulation (EEC) No. 1836/93 of 29 June 1993 Allowing Voluntary Participation by companies in the Industrial Sector in a Community Eco-Management and Audit Scheme 1993,

EU Directive on Integrated Pollution Prevention and Control (IPPC) [Council Directive 91/61/EC 1996, Concerning Integrated Pollution Prevention and Control, Official Journal of the European Communities, No. L257, , October 10, 1996;

<http://eippcb.jrc.es/pages/BActivities.cfm>.

Directive 91/61/EC 1996, related to Integrated Pollution Prevention and Control, Official Journal of the European Communities, No. L257, HMSO, London, October 10,

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Waste Management World Weekly E-Digest, 05 Augustus 2011.